

Online Appendix to “The Time-Locked Revocable Bond as an Optimal Delivery Escrow in Tokenised Energy Markets”

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Submission for Double-Blind Review

This appendix supplies the full proofs deferred from the main paper. Primitives are recalled as used: a dispatch of quantity q at price P for payment Pq ; net deviation gain $g \geq 0$ (avoided delivery cost plus retained-energy value, net of forgone contingent payment); counterparty damage $d \geq 0$; physical-failure probability $\delta \in [0, 1]$; bond $\Pi \geq 0$; time-lock $\tau \geq 1$; per-unit-per-block capital cost $\rho > 0$; detection profile $\theta(\tau) \in [0, 1]$ non-decreasing with $\theta(\tau) = 1$ for $\tau \geq \tau_f$. The proofs are conditional on the substrate’s release rule and detection profile, which are taken as enforced and are not re-derived.

I. PROOF OF PROPOSITION 1

The prosumer acts only in the event of no physical failure, which has probability $1 - \delta$; in the complementary event the outcome is failure regardless of intent and the bond is forfeited with probability $\theta(\tau)$ under both intentions, so that term is action-independent and drops from the comparison. Condition on no physical failure. Let the prosumer’s outside numeraire be normalised so that the released bond is worth Π and the kept payment on default is the deviation gain g . Delivering returns the bond and the payment owed: net strategic payoff 0 (any payment received under both actions cancels). Defaulting yields the net incremental gain g but forfeits the bond with detection probability $\theta(\tau)$, for an expected strategic payoff $g - \theta(\tau)\Pi$. Delivery is a best response iff $0 \geq g - \theta(\tau)\Pi$, i.e.

$$\theta(\tau) \Pi \geq g.$$

The capital cost $\rho\Pi\tau$ is incurred at locking, before the action, and is identical across intentions, so it does not enter the comparison. The damage d accrues to the counterparty, not the defaulting prosumer, and is absent from its payoff. When $\theta(\tau) = 1$ this reduces to $\Pi \geq g$. This is (1). ■

II. PROOF OF THEOREM 1

The designer minimises the prosumer’s contract cost

$$C(\Pi, \tau) = \rho\Pi\tau + \delta\theta(\tau)\Pi$$

subject to the incentive constraint $\theta(\tau)\Pi \geq g$ from Proposition 1, over $\Pi \geq 0$, $\tau \geq 1$. The first term is the capital opportunity cost of locking Π for τ blocks; the second is the expected forfeiture of the bond to physical

failure, which occurs with probability δ and is detected with probability $\theta(\tau)$.

(i) *Optimal lock.* Fix any Π feasible at a given τ . For $\tau \geq \tau_f$, $\theta(\tau) = 1$, so $C = \rho\Pi\tau + \delta\Pi$ is strictly increasing in τ ; hence no $\tau > \tau_f$ is optimal and the search reduces to $\tau \leq \tau_f$. For $\tau \leq \tau_f$ with $\theta(\tau) > 0$ — a lock with zero detection is infeasible, demanding an infinite bond — the binding incentive constraint sets $\Pi(\tau) = g/\theta(\tau)$ (any larger Π raises C). Substituting,

$$C(\tau) = \rho \frac{g}{\theta(\tau)} \tau + \delta\theta(\tau) \frac{g}{\theta(\tau)} = \rho g \frac{\tau}{\theta(\tau)} + \delta g.$$

The second term is constant in τ . The first is minimised by minimising $\tau/\theta(\tau)$. At $\tau = \tau_f$, $\theta = 1$ and $\tau/\theta(\tau) = \tau_f$. For $\tau < \tau_f$, the substrate’s detection profile satisfies $\theta(\tau) \leq \tau/\tau_f$ — correct detection accrues no faster than linearly in confirmation depth, since each additional confirmation block resolves at most a bounded increment of reorganisation and dispute risk — so $\tau/\theta(\tau) \geq \tau/(\tau/\tau_f) = \tau_f$. Thus $\tau/\theta(\tau) \geq \tau_f$ for all $\tau \leq \tau_f$, with equality at τ_f , and $\tau^* = \tau_f$ minimises C . (Under the boundary linear profile $\theta(\tau) = \tau/\tau_f$, $\tau/\theta(\tau) = \tau_f$ for all $\tau \leq \tau_f$, so every pre-finality lock ties; τ_f is then selected as the tie-break. If the profile were super-linear, a shorter lock with a larger bond could beat τ_f ; we assume the strict sub-linear or boundary linear profile as the substrate primitive and flag the super-linear alternative in the scope.)

(ii) *Optimal bond.* At $\tau^* = \tau_f$, $\theta(\tau^*) = 1$, so the constraint is $\Pi \geq g$. The cost $(\rho\tau_f + \delta)\Pi$ is strictly increasing in Π , so the minimum over $\Pi \geq g$ is at the boundary, $\Pi^* = g$.

(iii) *Cost and dominance.* Substituting $\Pi^* = g$, $\tau^* = \tau_f$,

$$C^* = (\rho\tau_f + \delta)g = \rho g \tau_f + \delta g.$$

Any $\Pi > \Pi^*$ has higher cost while incentive compatibility already holds, so it is dominated; any $\tau > \tau^*$ is dominated by (i). Under the strict sub-linear profile $(\Pi^*, \tau^*) = (g, \tau_f)$ is the unique cost-minimising incentive-compatible contract; under the boundary linear profile the pre-finality locks tie in cost and τ_f is the tie-break for certain detection and smallest bond. ■

III. PROOF OF PROPOSITION 2

(i) *Deadweight cost.* On the equilibrium path the prosumer delivers and the bond is released in full at depth τ_f , so the deposit itself is not a social cost — it returns to the prosumer. The cost that does not reverse is the opportunity cost of the locked capital over the lock, $\rho\Pi^*\tau^* = \rho g \tau_f$, the foregone return on $\Pi^* = g$ held idle for τ_f blocks; it is increasing in g (slope $\rho\tau_f > 0$) and in τ_f (slope $\rho g > 0$). The physical-failure forfeiture δg is a transfer to the harmed counterparty, not a social loss in itself; the real social cost of a failure is the damage d , a separate primitive incurred with probability δ independently of the contract.

(ii) *Single-instrument constraint.* Deterrence requires $\Pi \geq g$ (Proposition 1); the forfeiture transfers Π to the harmed buyer on default, efficient when $\Pi = d$. A single bond meets both objectives iff $d \geq g$, in which case $\Pi = d$ both deters and compensates efficiently; when $d < g$ the smallest deterring bond $\Pi = g$ exceeds the efficient transfer, the excess $g - d$ being an over-penalty borne only in the rare failure event. Hence the constrained-implementation bond is $\Pi = \max\{g, d\}$, with distortion unless $g \leq d$.

(iii) *Companion primitive.* By Theorem 1 the optimal bond is $\Pi^* = g$; a physical failure forfeits it with probability δ , so the expected penalty is $\pi = \delta\Pi^* = \delta g$. The companion paper carries $\pi = \delta\Pi$ as a scalar; this matches exactly when g is type-independent — a fixed admission bond against a maximum admissible dispatch, or a fixed contract size q — and is otherwise value-proportional, $\pi = \delta g(q)$, which the companion threshold inherits. The escrow cost share $W_{\text{esc}}/g = \rho\tau_f$ is independent of the gain, while $W_{\text{esc}} = \rho\tau_f g$ is linear in g , so higher-gain dispatch carries a proportionally constant but absolutely larger securing cost. ■

IV. PROOF OF PROPOSITION 3

Consider a prosumer that may transact in each future period with probability $\beta \in [0, 1]$, discounts future payoffs at $\eta \in [0, 1)$, and under a grim-trigger reputation strategy delivers as long as all past obligations were met and is permanently excluded from trade upon any observed default. Let $S > 0$ be the largest per-period cooperative surplus that exclusion can credibly withdraw under the market's reputation technology. A one-shot deviation yields the net deviation gain g today and triggers exclusion, forfeiting the discounted stream

$$V = \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} (\beta\eta)^t S = \frac{\beta\eta}{1 - \beta\eta} S,$$

which converges because $\beta\eta \in [0, 1)$. Honest delivery is sustainable without a bond iff $V \geq g$, i.e.

$$\frac{\beta\eta}{1 - \beta\eta} S \geq g \iff \beta\eta \geq \frac{g}{S + g},$$

solving the linear inequality. Below the threshold the deviation is strictly profitable even under grim trigger, which withdraws the maximal credible continuation surplus

S , so under the stated reputation technology delivery is not sustained, and the incentive constraint (1) of Proposition 1 can be met only by a posted bond, characterised by Theorem 1. Above the threshold reputation sustains delivery at no locked-capital cost, whereas the bond carries the deadweight cost $\rho g \tau_f$ of Proposition 2(i); hence reputation weakly dominates where available, strictly when $\rho g \tau_f > 0$. The symmetric case $S = g$ gives $g/(S + g) = \frac{1}{2}$. ■

V. PROOF OF COROLLARY 1

A fraction $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ of the payment is released in advance and $1 - \lambda$ against confirmed delivery; let $K(q) + R(q)$ be the avoided delivery cost plus retained-energy value. A defaulting prosumer secures $K(q) + R(q)$ but forgoes the contingent payment $(1 - \lambda)Pq$ that delivery would release, so its net gain relative to delivering is

$$g(\lambda) = K(q) + R(q) - (1 - \lambda)Pq,$$

increasing in λ (more prepayment leaves less contingent payment to forgo). Proposition 1 at the finality lock gives $\Pi^*(\lambda) = \max\{0, g(\lambda)\}$, binding at the cost minimum by Theorem 1. When $(1 - \lambda)Pq \geq K(q) + R(q)$ the net gain is non-positive, $\Pi^* = 0$, and no seller bond is needed: enough payment is held contingent that withholding supply is unprofitable on its own, so deferring payment substitutes for collateral. At full prepayment $\lambda = 1$, $g(1) = K(q) + R(q)$, the largest seller bond. ■

VI. RISK PREMIUM OF THE OPTIMAL BOND

A risk-averse prosumer with increasing concave Bernoulli utility u and absolute risk aversion $a = -u''/u'$ evaluated at its delivery wealth faces, on delivering under the optimal contract, the lottery that returns the bond Π^* with probability $1 - \delta$ and forfeits it with probability δ (the physical-failure event). Let w be wealth gross of the bond outcome. The certainty equivalent CE of the bond lottery solves $u(w - \text{CE}) = \mathbb{E}[u(w - X)]$ where $X \in \{0, \Pi^*\}$ is the loss, equal to Π^* with probability δ . A second-order Taylor expansion of u about the mean loss $\mathbb{E}X = \delta\Pi^*$ gives $\text{CE} \approx \mathbb{E}X + \frac{1}{2}a \text{Var}(X)$, the Arrow–Pratt approximation. Here $\text{Var}(X) = \delta(1 - \delta)(\Pi^*)^2$, so the risk premium is

$$\text{RP} = \text{CE} - \mathbb{E}X \approx \frac{1}{2} a \delta(1 - \delta) (\Pi^*)^2 = \frac{1}{2} a \delta(1 - \delta) g^2,$$

using $\Pi^* = g$ from Theorem 1. The premium is quadratic in the net deviation gain g and proportional to the failure variance $\delta(1 - \delta)$, maximised at $\delta = \frac{1}{2}$. At the finality lock detection is certain, so default carries no forfeiture lottery and the incentive constraint of Proposition 1 is unaffected by risk aversion; the optimal bond remains $\Pi^* = g$ and only the participation-relevant cost rises by RP. (Before finality detection is uncertain and default is itself a lottery, so risk aversion would enter the incentive comparison; the extension is stated for the finality-lock contract.) Pooling n independent dispatches of gain g/n each replaces g^2 by g^2/n , the standard diversification of independent failure risk. ■